

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Asymptotic Distribution of Eigenvalues of Non-Self Adjoint Differential Operators

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Abstract

The study of non-self-adjoint differential operators is a historical issue. Before and until now, most studies of operator theory have been about self-adjoint operators. But non-self-adjoint operators have recently found many applications in other sciences. These operators have received much attention in thermodynamics and quantum mechanics. Because there is no general spectral theory for these operators, it is more difficult to study these operators than the self-adjoint type. The spectrum of these operators is usually unstable and their resolvent is unpredictable. In this paper by use of Weyl's law for asymptotic distribution of eigenvalues of elliptic self adjoint operators on bounded domain, we consider a second-order non-self-adjoint differential operator and study its distribution of eigenvalues. Our goal is to find an asymptotic formula for the Dirichlet eigenvalue counting function on the open interval $(0, 1)$.

Keywords: resolvent; distribution of eigenvalues; non-self-adjoint operators; elliptic operators; asymptotic distribution of eigenvalues

Mathematics Subject Classification: 46E35, 47A10

1 Introduction

Numerous articles have been written on the asymptotic distribution of linear operators and Weyl's law. For example, the reader may consult [18] in which one can see the historical course and evolution of this law about 100 years after its inception. Also in [19], some interesting progress has been made in this field. In this article, we follow the works of K. Kh. Boimatov in [4], [3], [6] and the works of A. Sameripour in [10], [11], [15] and Vulis and M. Z. Solomyak in [16]. In [3] K. Kh. Boimatov proposed an asymptotic formula for the distribution of the eigenvalues of the following operator

$$(Py)(t) = -(t^\alpha A(t)y'(t))' + C(t)y(t),$$

with matrix coefficients

$$A(t) \in C^\infty(\bar{J}, \text{End}\mathbb{C}^n), C(t) \in C(\bar{J}, \text{End}\mathbb{C}^n),$$

where $\alpha \in [0, 2)$, $t \in \bar{J} = [0, 1]$, $y \in L^2(J)$. In [15], A. Sameripour, Y. Yadollahi obtained the asymptotic formula for the distribution of eigenvalues of a non-self-adjoint elliptic linear differential operator in Hilbert space. In this paper, we consider a non-self-adjoint elliptic differential operator in a Hilbert space and, in addition to estimating its resolvent, distribute the asymptotic distribution of its eigenvalues. Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be a bounded domain with smooth boundary $\partial\Omega \in C^\infty$. By use of Weyl's law for asymptotic distribution of eigenvalues of elliptic self adjoint operators on a bounded domain, we study the asymptotic distribution of eigenvalues of non-self adjoint elliptic systems of the differential operator A defined in the space $H_\ell = L^2(\Omega)^\ell$ by: $(Au)(x) = -\sum_{i,j=1}^n (\rho^{2\alpha}(x)a_{ij}(x)q(x)u'_{x_i}(x))'_{x_j}$, where $\rho \in C^1([0, 1], \mathbb{R})$ is the weight function $\alpha \in [1, 0)$, $a_{ij}(x) = \overline{a_{ji}(x)}$ ($i, j = 1, 2, \dots, n$), with $a_{ij}(x) \in C^2(\bar{\Omega})$, $|s|^2 \leq M \sum_{i,j=1}^n a_{ij}(x)s_i \bar{s}_j$, ($x \in \Omega$, and there exist $M > 0$, $s = (s_1, \dots, s_n) \in \mathbb{C}^n$), $q(x) \in C^2(\bar{\Omega}, \text{End}\mathbb{C}^\ell)$. Furthermore, let for $\forall x \in \bar{\Omega}$, the matrix function $q(x)$ has simple eigenvalues $\mu_1(x), \dots, \mu_\ell(x)$ that lie on the complex plane outside of the sector $S \subset \Phi \setminus \mathbb{R}_+$ where $\Phi = \{z \in \mathbb{C} : |\arg z| < \varphi\}$, $\varphi \in (0, \pi)$. If $\rho(x) = \text{dist}\{x, \partial\Omega\}$ then this operator is the one that has already been discussed by A. Sameripour and K. Sddighi in [10], [11]. We introduce the space

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$\mathcal{H}_\ell = W_{2,\alpha}^{2\ell}(\Omega)^\ell = W_{2,\alpha}^2(\Omega) \times \dots \times W_{2,\alpha}^2(\Omega)$ (ℓ -times) as the space of vector functions $u(x) = (u_1(x), \dots, u_\ell(x))$ defined on Ω with the finite norm

$$|u, W_{2,\alpha}^2(\Omega)| = \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \int \rho^{2\alpha}(x) |u'_{x_i}(x)|_{\mathbb{C}^\ell}^2 dx + \int_\Omega |u(x)|_{\mathbb{C}^\ell}^2 \right)^{1/2}.$$

We denote by $\mathring{\mathcal{H}}_\ell$ the closure of $C_0^\infty(\Omega)^\ell$ in \mathcal{H}_ℓ with respect to the above norm. Let $D(A) = \{u \in \mathring{\mathcal{H}}_\ell \cap W_{2,loc}^2(\Omega)^\ell : \sum_{i,j=1}^n (\rho^{2\alpha} a_{ij} q u'_{x_i})'_{x_j} \in H_\ell\}$ and $W_{2,loc}^2(\Omega) = \{u : \sum_{i=0}^2 \int_J |u^{(i)}(x)|^2 dx < \infty, J \subset \Omega, \text{ open}\}$. The assumptions we have made here about the operator and its domain make it possible to use the first representation theorem to convert this operator to an appropriate m -sectorial operator by multiplying by a suitable complex number. m -sectorial operators are well-known operators in operator theory that have many applications (For further details, see, e.g., [8]). Such a conversion makes it easier to find the resolvent of the operator.

2 On the Resolvent and Asymptotic Distribution of Eigenvalues of Linear Operator A

First, we will discuss some examples, then we will state Weyl's theorem, and accordingly we will reach the main theorems of this article.

Example 2.1. Let a, b, c be real numbers, $a < 0$, and $L(y) = ay'' + by' + cy$ be a differential operator defined in $L^2(0, 1)$ on field of real numbers with boundary Dirichlet conditions. First we find the eigenvalues of this operator. If λ is a eigenvalue of this operator then by $L(y) = ay'' + by' + cy = \lambda y$ we understand that λ is real. The characteristic equation of this linear differential equation is $ar^2 + br + (c - \lambda) = 0$. The roots of this equation are $r_{1,2} = \frac{-b \pm \sqrt{b^2 - 4a(c - \lambda)}}{2a}$. If these roots are real, then λ is not a eigenvalue. So $r_{1,2}$ are complex and the general solution of the differential equation $ay'' + by' + cy = \lambda y$ is $y = e^{\varphi x} (A \cos(\phi x) + B \sin(\phi x))$, where $\varphi = -\frac{b}{2a}$, $\phi = \frac{\sqrt{-(b^2 - 4a(c - \lambda))}}{2a}$. So the eigenvalues of this operator are $\lambda_k = -ak^2\pi^2 - \frac{b^2 - 4ac}{4a}, k = 1, 2, \dots$. And so we have

$$N(\tau) = \# \left\{ k \in \mathbb{N} : -ak^2\pi^2 - \frac{b^2 - 4ac}{4a} < \tau \right\},$$

and finally $N(\tau) \sim \frac{\sqrt{\tau}}{\pi\sqrt{-a}}$ as $\tau \rightarrow \infty$.

Example 2.2. In this example we consider the self-adjoint second order differential operator $Au(t) = \frac{d^2u(t)}{dt^2}$ in Hilbert space $L^2(0, 1)$ with Dirichlet boundary conditions. If λ is an eigenvalue of this operator then $\frac{d^2u(t)}{dt^2} = \lambda u(t)$, and then the eigenvalues of the linear operator A are $\lambda_k = (k\pi)^2, k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$,

$$N(\tau) = \# \left\{ k \in \mathbb{N} : (k\pi)^2 < \tau \right\} = \# \left\{ k \in \mathbb{N} : k < \frac{\sqrt{\tau}}{\pi} \right\} \sim \frac{\sqrt{\tau}}{\pi}$$

Example 2.3. Let $\Omega = (0, 1) \times (0, 1)$. Find the eigenvalues of Laplacian operator on Ω with Dirichlet boundary conditions.

Solution. We have to solve the second-order differential equation $\Delta u = \lambda u$. Using the idea of separation of variables, this can be written as $u(x, y) = f(x)g(y)$. So the equation $\Delta u = \lambda u$ turns into $\frac{f''(x)}{f(x)} + \frac{g''(y)}{g(y)} = \lambda$. And $\frac{f''(x)}{f(x)} = \lambda_x, \frac{g''(y)}{g(y)} = \lambda_y, \lambda = \lambda_x + \lambda_y$. By using $f(0) = f(1) = 0, g(0) = g(1) = 0$ the result is $f(x) = \sin(nx), g(y) = \sin(my)$, for $m, n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$. Therefore

$$u_{mn}(x, y) = \sin(nx) \sin(my), \lambda_{mn} = \pi^2(m^2 + n^2), m, n = 1, 2, 3, \dots,$$

and the eigenvalues are $\lambda_{mn} = \pi^2(m^2 + n^2), m, n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$

$$N(\tau) = \# \left\{ (m, n) : \lambda_{mn} = \pi^2(m^2 + n^2) < \tau \right\} = \# \left\{ (m, n) : m^2 + n^2 < \frac{\tau}{\pi^2} \right\}.$$

Let $E_\tau = \left\{ (x, y) \in \mathbb{R}^2 : x^2 + y^2 < \frac{\tau}{\pi^2}, x, y \geq 0 \right\}$, then $N(\tau)$ is the number of integer lattices points in E_τ

$$N(\tau) = \sum_{(m,n) \in \mathbb{N}^2, \lambda_{mn} < \tau} \text{area}(m-1, m) \times (n-1, n) \leq \text{area } E_\tau = \frac{\tau}{4\pi}.$$

Theorem 2.1 ([25]). Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be a bounded domain, and $N(\lambda)$ be the Dirichlet eigenvalue counting function on Ω , then

$$N(\lambda) \sim c_n \text{vol}(\Omega) \lambda^{\frac{n}{2}},$$

where $c_n = \frac{\omega_n}{(2\pi)^n}$ is a constant depending only on the dimension n , and ω_n is the volume of the unit ball in \mathbb{R}^n .

Theorem 2.2. Let $S \subset \Phi \setminus \mathbb{R}_+$ be some closed sector with vertex at 0, and let for $\forall x \in \bar{\Omega}$, the matrix function $q(x)$ have simple eigenvalues $\mu_1(x), \dots, \mu_\ell(x)$ arranged in the complex plane outside of the closed sector $S \subset \Phi \setminus \mathbb{R}_+$ where $\mu_j(x) \notin S$ for $j = 1, \dots, \ell$. Then, for sufficiently large in modules $\lambda \in S$ the inverse operator $(A - \lambda I)^{-1}$ exists and is continuous, and the following estimate is valid

$$\|(A - \lambda I)^{-1}\| \leq M_S |\lambda|^{-1} \quad (\lambda \in S, |\lambda| \geq C_S),$$

where M_S, C_S are sufficiently large numbers. Here, and in the sequel, the value of the function $\arg z \in (-\pi, \pi]$, and $\|T\|$ denotes the norm of the bounded operator T on H_ℓ .

Proof. We first find the estimates of the resolvent of the operators P_k ($k = 1, 2, \dots, \ell$), defined on $\mathcal{H} = \mathcal{H}_1$ by

$$(P_k y)(x) = - \sum_{i,j=1}^n (\rho^{2\alpha}(x) a_{ij}(x) \mu_k(x) y'_{x_i}(x))'_{x_j},$$

$$D(P_k) = \{y \in \overset{\circ}{\mathcal{H}} \cap W_{2,loc}^2(\Omega) : \sum_{i,j=1}^n (\rho^{2\alpha} a_{ij} \mu_k y'_{x_i})'_{x_j} \in H\}.$$

The eigenvalues $\mu_k(x)$ of $q(x)$ are clearly in $C^2(\bar{\Omega})$, $k = 1, \dots, \ell$. Now for $k \in \{v+1, \dots, \ell\}$ we construct the nonnegative functions, $\varphi_{k_1}(x), \dots, \varphi_{k_m}(x) \in C^\infty(\bar{\Omega})$ satisfying these conditions: $\sum_{i=1}^m \varphi_{k_i}^2(x) \equiv 1$ ($x \in \bar{\Omega}$) and so

$|\arg\{\mu_k(x_1)\mu_k^{-1}(x_2)\}| < \frac{\pi}{16}$ for each $x_1, x_2 \in \text{supp } \varphi_{k_i}$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$, we also assume that $\varphi < \frac{\pi}{16}$. Now we construct functions $\mu_{k_r}(x) \in C^2(\bar{\Omega})$ satisfying the conditions: $\mu_{k_r}(x) = \mu_k(x)$, ($\forall x \in \text{supp } \varphi_{k_r}$), $\mu_{k_r}(x) \notin \bar{\Phi}$, ($\forall x \in \bar{\Omega}$), $|\arg\{\mu_{k_r}(x_1)\mu_{k_r}^{-1}(x_2)\}| < \frac{\pi}{8}$, ($\forall x_1, x_2 \in \bar{\Omega}$). For $k = v+1, \dots, \ell$ and $r = 1, \dots, m$ there exist numbers $Z_{k_r} \in \mathbb{C}$, such that $|Z_{k_r}| = 1, \forall x \in \bar{\Omega}$, $\lambda \in \bar{\Phi}$ we have

$$c' \leq \text{Re}\{Z_{k_r} \mu_{k_r}(x)\}, \quad c' |\lambda| \leq -\text{Re}\{Z_{k_r} \lambda\}, \quad c' > 0. \tag{2.1}$$

By using the functions $\mu_{k_r}(x)$, $k = v+1, \dots, \ell$ we can define in H the following operators:

$$(P_{k_r} y)(x) = - \sum_{i,j=1}^n (\rho^{2\alpha}(x) a_{ij}(x) \mu_{k_r}(x) y'_{x_i}(x))'_{x_j},$$

$$D(P_{k_r}) = \{y \in \overset{\circ}{\mathcal{H}} \cap W_{2,loc}^2(\Omega) : \sum_{i,j=1}^n (\rho^{2\alpha} a_{ij} \mu_{k_r} y'_{x_i})'_{x_j} \in H\}.$$

Take $I(y) = \sum_{i=1}^n \int_{\Omega} \rho^{2\alpha}(x) |y'_{x_i}(x)|^2 dx$, then from uniformly elliptic condition we have for $c > 0$:

$$c \sum_{i=1}^n |y'_{x_i}(x)|^2 \leq \sum_{i,j=1}^n a_{ij}(x) y'_{x_i}(x) \overline{y'_{x_j}(x)} = \langle a(x) \nabla_x y(x), \nabla_x y(x) \rangle_{\mathbb{C}^n},$$

Then for $y \in D(P_{k_r})$, $k = 1, \dots, \ell$ according to (2.1) we have:

$$I(y) \leq M_1 \text{Re}\{Z_{k_r} \sum_{i,j=1}^n (\rho^\alpha a_{ij} \mu_{k_r} y'_{x_i}, \rho^\alpha y'_{x_j})\} = M_1 \text{Re}\{Z_{k_r} (P_{k_r} y, y)\}. \tag{2.2}$$

Here and in the sequel, the symbol (\cdot) denotes the inner product in H .

By (2.1) we have: $c' |\lambda| \leq -\text{Re}\{Z_{k_r} \lambda\}$, $c' > 0, \forall \lambda \in \Phi$.

Multiply this inequality by $\int_{\Omega} |y(x)|^2 dx = (y, y) = \|y\|^2 > 0$. It follows that

$$c' |\lambda| \int_{\Omega} |y(x)|^2 dx \leq -\text{Re}\{Z_{k_r} \lambda\} (y, y).$$

From this and by (2.2) we will have

$$I(y) + c' |\lambda| \int_{\Omega} |y(x)|^2 dx \leq \text{Re} Z_{k_r} \{(P_{k_r} y, y) - \lambda (y, y)\}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \operatorname{Re} Z_{k_r}((P_{k_r} - \lambda I)y, y) \\
 &\leq \|Z_{k_r}\| |y|_H |(P_{k_r} - \lambda I)y|_H \\
 &= |y|_H |(P_{k_r} - \lambda I)y|_H.
 \end{aligned}$$

This implies that

$$|\lambda| |y|_H^2 \leq M |y|_H |(P_{k_r} - \lambda I)y|_H, \tag{2.3}$$

$$I(y) \leq |y|_H |(P_{k_r} - \lambda I)y|_H, \tag{2.4}$$

(2.3) ensures that the operator $(P_{k_r} - \lambda I)$ is one to one, which implies that $\ker(P_{k_r} - \lambda I) = 0$. Therefore the inverse operator $(P_{k_r} - \lambda I)^{-1}$ exists, and is continuous.

put $y = (P_{k_r} - \lambda I)^{-1}f$, $f \in H$ in (2.3), we conclude that

$$|\lambda| |(P_{k_r} - \lambda I)^{-1}f|_H^2 \leq M |(P_{k_r} - \lambda I)^{-1}f|_H |(P_{k_r} - \lambda I)(P_{k_r} - \lambda I)^{-1}f|_H$$

i.e.,

$$|\lambda| |(P_{k_r} - \lambda I)^{-1}f|_H \leq M |f|_H$$

hence

$$\|(P_{k_r} - \lambda I)^{-1}\| \leq M |\lambda|^{-1}. \tag{2.5}$$

put $y = (P_{k_r} - \lambda I)^{-1}f$, $f \in H$ in (2.4) and using (2.5) implies that

$$\begin{aligned}
 |\rho^\alpha \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (P_{k_r} - \lambda I)^{-1}f|_H^2 &\leq |(P_{k_r} - \lambda I)^{-1}f|_H |(P_{k_r} - \lambda I)(P_{k_r} - \lambda I)^{-1}f|_H \\
 &\leq |(P_{k_r} - \lambda I)^{-1}f|_H |f|_H \\
 &\leq M |f|^2 |\lambda|^{-1}
 \end{aligned}$$

hence,

$$\|\rho^\alpha \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (P_{k_r} - \lambda I)^{-1}\|_H \leq M |\lambda|^{-\frac{1}{2}}.$$

From here, according to Hardy’s inequality and the above observations, we conclude that

$$\|\rho^{2\alpha-1} (P_{k_r} - \lambda I)^{-1}\| \leq M_3 \sum_{i=1}^n \|\rho^\alpha \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (P_{k_r} - \lambda I)^{-1}\| \leq M' |\lambda|^{-\frac{1}{2}}. \tag{2.6}$$

Let us introduce the operator:

$$G_k(\lambda) = \sum_{r=1}^m \varphi_{k_r} (P_{k_r} - \lambda I)^{-1} \varphi_{k_r}, \quad (k = 1, \dots, \ell)$$

in the space \mathcal{H}_ℓ . Here φ_{k_r} is the operator of multiplication by function $\varphi_{k_r}(x)$; It is easily verified that

$$\begin{aligned}
 (P_k - \lambda I)G_k(\lambda) &= I + \rho^{2\alpha-1}(x) \sum_{r=1}^m B_{k_r}(x) (P_{k_r} - \lambda I)^{-1} \varphi_{k_r} + \\
 &+ \rho^{2\alpha}(x) \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{r=1}^m \gamma_{k_{ir}}(x) \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (P_{k_r} - \lambda I)^{-1} \varphi_{k_r},
 \end{aligned}$$

where $\beta_{k_r}, \gamma_{k_{ir}}(x) \in L_\infty(\Omega)$, $(x \in \Omega)$ are bounded functions, $\operatorname{supp} \beta_{k_r}, \operatorname{supp} \gamma_{k_{ir}}(x) \subset \operatorname{supp} \varphi_{k_r}$.

Applying (2.5)-(2.6) then we will have:

$$\|(P_k - \lambda I)G_k(\lambda) - I\| \leq M |\lambda|^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad (\lambda \in \overline{\Phi}, |\lambda| \geq 1)$$

Thus for $k = 1, \dots, \ell$ we have the representation:

$$(P_k - \lambda I)^{-1} = G_k(\lambda)(I + F_k(\lambda)), \quad \|F_k(\lambda)\| \leq M |\lambda|^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad (\lambda \in \overline{\Phi}, |\lambda| \geq C_5) \tag{2.7}$$

It readily follows that $\|(P_k - \lambda I)^{-1}\| \leq M |\lambda|^{-1}$.

Thus here for $k = 1, \dots, \ell$, we obtain the resolvent of the operators P_k , i.e., we implies that

$$\|(P_k - \lambda I)^{-1}\| \leq M|\lambda|^{-1} \quad (\lambda \in S, |\lambda| \geq C_S), k = 1, \dots, \ell,$$

We now diagonalize the matrix function $q(x)$ as follows:

$$q(x) = U(x)\Lambda(x)U^{-1}(x), \text{ where } U(x), U^{-1}(x) \in C^2(\bar{\Omega}, \text{End } \mathbf{C}^\ell)$$

and

$$\Lambda(x) = \text{diag}\{\mu_1(x), \dots, U_\ell(x)\}.$$

Let $\Gamma(\lambda) = UB(\lambda)U^{-1}$, that the operator $B(\lambda)$ in the direct sum.

$$H_\ell = H \oplus \dots \oplus H \quad (\ell\text{-times})$$

has the representation:

$$B(\lambda) = \text{diag}\{(P_1 - \lambda I)^{-1}, \dots, (P_\ell - \lambda I)^{-1}\},$$

such that $\lambda \in \bar{\phi} \setminus R_+, |\lambda| \geq C_S, (Uu)(x) = U(x)u(x), (u \in H_\ell)$.

It is easily verified

$$(A - \lambda I)\Gamma(\lambda) = I + \rho^{2\alpha-1}(x)q_0(x)B(\lambda)U^{-1} + \rho^{2\alpha}(x) \sum_{i=1}^n q_i(x) \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} B(\lambda)U^{-1},$$

$q_i(x) \in C(\bar{\Omega}, \text{End } \mathbf{C}^\ell), i = 0, 1, \dots, n$, Applying (2.5)-(2.7) we have as in (2.7):

$$(A - \lambda I)^{-1} = \Gamma(\lambda)(I + F(\lambda))$$

$$\|F(\lambda)\| \leq M_\psi |\lambda|^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad (\lambda \in \Phi_\psi, |\lambda| \geq C_S).$$

Consequently, it readily follows that

$$\|(A - \lambda I)^{-1}\| \leq M_\psi |\lambda|^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad (\lambda \in S, |\lambda| \geq C_S).$$

This complete the proof of Theorem 2.2. □

Theorem 2.3. For $\alpha \in [0, 1)$ by using [16] the following statements hold:

(i) if $\alpha < \frac{1}{n}$ then we have

$$N(t) \sim (2\pi)^{-n} V_n t^{n/2} \int_\Omega \rho^{-n\alpha}(x) \mu(x) (\det a(x))^{-\frac{1}{2}} dx,$$

where V_n denotes the volume of the unit ball in R^n ,

$$a(x) = (a_{ij}(x))_{i,j=1}^n, \quad \mu(x) = \sum_{k=1}^v \mu_k^{-\frac{n}{2}}(x),$$

(ii) If $\alpha = \frac{1}{n}$, then we have:

$$N(t) \sim \frac{nV_n}{(2n-2)(2\pi)^n} t^{\frac{n}{2}} \log t \int_{\partial\Omega} \frac{\mu ds}{\sqrt{\det a}},$$

(iii) If $\alpha > \frac{1}{n}$, then we have:

$$N(t) \sim \frac{V_{n-1}}{(2\pi)^{n-1}} t^\delta \omega_0 \int_{\partial\Omega} \mu_0 (\det a)^{-\frac{1}{2}} (af, f)_{\mathbf{C}^n}^{\frac{n}{2}-\delta} ds,$$

where $\delta = \frac{n-1}{2-2\alpha}, \mu_0(x) = \sum_{j=1}^v \mu_j^{-\delta}(x), \omega_0 = \sum_{j=1}^{+\infty} \beta_j^{-\delta}$, where β_j are the eigenvalues of the auxiliary Sturm-Liouville differential equation below;

$$-(\tau^{2\alpha} y'(\tau))^{2\alpha} y(\tau) = \beta y(\tau), \quad \tau \in R_+, y \in L_2(R_+), y(0) = 0.$$

$f(x)$ is a unit normal vector on $\partial\Omega$ at the point x . (Noteworthy is that an important example explaining the matter of asymptotic distribution of eigenvalues is given by Vulis and Solomyak in [16]).

Proof. The asymptotic spectrum of a non-self-adjoint elliptic differential operator A for analogous conditions, i.e. $\alpha < \frac{1}{n}$, is treated in [1,2,4], the case $n = 1$ is considered in [1,2]. We define $N(t) = \text{card}\{j : |\lambda_j| \leq t\}$, $t > 0$. For our later work we define $\omega = \max\{\frac{n}{2}, \frac{n-1}{2-2\alpha}\}$. To establish the assertion of Theorem 2.3., we use [16] and M. V. Keldish's theorem of Tauberian-type for the case $\omega \neq 1$ and the multidimensional Tauberian Theorems of A. A. Shkalikov [12] for the case $\omega \in \mathbf{N}$, and by establish the following assertion we can prove Theorem 2.3.

Now for every natural number s , such that

$$s \in \mathbf{N}, s > \omega = \max\{\frac{n}{2}, \frac{n-1}{2-2\alpha}\}, \quad s \in (\omega, \omega + 1],$$

we will have

$$|tr (A - \lambda I)^{-s} - tr UB(\lambda)^s U^{-1}| \leq M|\lambda|^{-\frac{1}{2}}|\Gamma(\lambda)|_s^s,$$

where the symbols $tr, |\cdot|_s$ denote the trace of a trace-class operator and the σ_s -norm of the operator ([7]).

By using the representation of the operator $B(\lambda)$ we obtain

$$tr UB(\lambda)^s U^{-1} = tr B(\lambda)^s = tr B_s(\lambda),$$

where $B_s(\lambda) = \text{diag}\{(P_1 - \lambda I)^{-s}, \dots, (P_\ell - \lambda I)^{-s}\}$. If we estimate $|\Gamma(\lambda)|_s^s$ by using (2.5) and (2.7) we obtain

$$|\sum_{i=1}^{+\infty} (\lambda'_i - \lambda)^{-s} - \sum_{j=1}^{\ell} \sum_{i=1}^{+\infty} (\lambda_{ij} - \lambda)^{-s}| \leq M_\psi |\lambda|^{\omega-s-\frac{1}{4}}, \quad (\lambda \in \Phi_\psi, |\lambda| \geq C_\psi),$$

where $\lambda'_1, \lambda'_2, \dots, \lambda_{1j}, \lambda_{2j}, \dots$ denote the eigenvalues of the operators A and P_j respectively. Notice that according to (2.7), there are a finite number of eigenvalues of the operators P_{v+1}, \dots, P_ℓ in the angle Φ . Hence using contour integral method as in [5,§4] for $\omega \neq 1, 2, \dots$ we can obtain the relation

$$\sum_{i=1}^{+\infty} (\lambda'_i + \tau)^{-s} = \sum_{j=1}^v \sum_{i=1}^{+\infty} (\lambda_{ij} + \tau)^{-s} + O(\tau^{\omega-s-\frac{1}{4}}), \quad \tau \rightarrow \infty.$$

Keeping in mind that $\lambda_{ij} > 0$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, j = 1, \dots, v$), it is easy to establish the asymptotical formula

$$\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{dN(t)}{(t + \tau)^s} \sim \sum_{i=1}^v \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{dN_i(t)}{(t + \tau)^s}, \quad \tau \rightarrow +\infty.$$

From the Tauberain Theorem of Keldish we have

$$N(t) \sim Ct^\omega \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \alpha \neq \frac{1}{n}, \\ \log t & \text{if } \alpha = \frac{1}{n}, (t \rightarrow +\infty). \end{cases}$$

□

3 Conclusion

In this paper, our aim was to investigate the resolvent of a second-order non-self-adjoint elliptic differential operator and to estimate its resolvent operator. Then, in the last theorem, we established an asymptotic formula for the distribution of the eigenvalues of this operator.

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